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**Language choice in Friday sermons:
Standard Arabic vs Moroccan Arabic**

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Consonants

Symbol	Place of Articulation	Manner of Articulation	Arabic
/t/	Alveolar	Stop	ت
/d/	Alveolar	Stop	د
/z/	Alveolar	Fricative	ز
/s/	Alveolar	Fricative	س
/n/	Alveolar	Nasal	ن
/l/	Alveolar	Lateral approximant	ل
/r/	Alveolar / Alveolar trill	Flap / Trill	ر
/b/	Bilabial	Stop	ب
/m/	Bilabial	Nasal	م
/θ/	Dental / Interdental	Fricative	ث
/ð/	Dental / Interdental	Fricative	ذ
/h/	Glottal / Pharyngeal	Fricative	ه
/w/	Labio-velar	Approximant	و
/f/	Labiodental	Fricative	ف
/j/	Palatal	Approximant	ي
/sʕ/	Pharyngeal	Fricative	ص
/dʕ/	Pharyngeal	Stop	ض
/ʕ/	Pharyngeal / Glottal	Fricative or Approximant	ع
/tʕ/	Pharyngeal / Retroflexion	Stop	ط
/ʃ/	Post-alveolar	Fricative	ش
/q/	Uvular	Stop	ق
/ʁ/	Uvular or Pharyngeal	Fricative	غ
/k/	Velar	Stop	ك

Vowels

Symbol	Length		
/a/	Short	Central (or slightly fronted)	Open (low)
/a:/	Long	Central (or slightly fronted)	Open (low)
/i/	Short	Front	Close (high)
/i:/	Long	Front	Close (high)
/u/	Short	Back	Close (high) + Rounded
/u:/	Long	Back	Close (high) + Rounded

Introduction

In Morocco, the sociolinguistic situation is characterized by a phenomenon known as Diglossia, where two distinct varieties of the same language co-exist within the same speech community. Standard Arabic (SA), known as the language of the Qur'an, holds a high position in society. To the contrary, Moroccan Arabic (Darija), the language of the majority, is commonly used in informal settings. This dichotomy becomes particularly observable in religious contexts, such as Friday sermons *khutba*, where language choice can somehow impact the delivery and the receiving of the message.

In Islam jurisprudence, the Friday sermon *khutba* is traditionally required to be delivered in Classic or Standard Arabic to maintain the sanctity of religious speech. (Athmane 2024) highlights this tradition by citing Ibn Taymiyya's view that "Arabic is in itself part of religion, and knowing it is an obligation, because understanding the Koran and Sunnah is an obligation that cannot be attained without the Arabic language" (p.64). Similarly, Ennaji (2005) emphasizes that "Classical Arabic is the variety used in formal religious sermons and in the Qur'an," (p.52). However, in Moroccan mosques, while the *khutba* is usually delivered in Classical Arabic, Imams often use Moroccan Arabic (Darija) to explain or emphasize certain points for better understanding. This practice is generally accepted as helpful for clarity rather than a deviation from tradition. The four Sunni schools of thought share a similar view, where the *khutba* must be in Arabic: the Hanafi school allows dialects for clarification outside the sermon (Al-Baz, 2010), the Maliki school permits simple dialectal explanations (Zuhayli, 2005), the Shafi'i school insists on Classical Arabic but allows local dialects informally (Ash-Shafi'i, 2009), and the Hanbali school similarly restricts the sermon to Arabic but allows dialect use informally (Ibn Qudamah, 2008).

This study investigates how Imams in Moroccan mosques balance Standard Arabic and Moroccan Arabic in Friday sermons. By examining the sociolinguistic factors influencing language choice in *khutba*, the research aims to understand the broader implications of this linguistic practice, and the status of Moroccan Arabic.

2 Review of The Literature

2.1 Introduction

This literature review explores the linguistic phenomenon of diglossia. It begins with a definition of diglossia and its key characteristics. The review then examines the function and prestige of the High (H) and Low (L) varieties, their roles in literary heritage, and how they are acquired by speakers. The stability of diglossia over time, along with grammatical and lexical differences between H and L varieties, will also be analyzed. Additionally, the review will deal with the relationship between diglossia and code-switching, as well as the use of diglossia in religious discourse, particularly in Friday sermons and other religious settings.

2.2 Diglossia

2.2.1 Definition of Diglossia

In Morocco, people often use two forms of Arabic: Standard Arabic (SA) and Moroccan Arabic (MA) also known as Darija. SA is the formal version, used in Formal settings, education, and official speeches. “It is also the prestigious register which conveys the words of the Qur’an and the religious discourse”. (Chekayri 2006:41)

Darija is the everyday spoken language, used in daily conversations. This situation, where two language varieties are used for different purposes, is known as **diglossia**. Sociolinguists consider both SA and MA as varieties of the same language, used by speakers in different social contexts for different functions. As for Ferguson 1959: 75 he defines diglossia as :

a relatively stable language situation in which, in addition to the primary dialects of the language (which may include a standard or regional standards), there is a very divergent, highly codified (often grammatically more complex) superposed variety, the vehicle of a large and respected body of written literature, either of an earlier period or in another speech community, which is learned largely by formal education and is used for

most written and formal spoken purposes but is not used by any sector of the community for ordinary conversation.

In this definition, Ferguson points out to multiple differences between (1) spoken and written forms, (2) between two types of language—High variety (H), which is the more formal type, and Low variety (L), which is more informal. The H variety is usually learned in school through reading and writing, while the L variety is acquired as a first language. the H variety is used for writing and formal speech, while the L variety is used in casual, everyday conversations.

2.2.2 Characteristics of Diglossia

In diglossia, the High (H) and Low (L) varieties each has it's own job, and they're not usually used in the same situations. For example, H is used in religious sermons, political speeches, news broadcasts, and formal writing. L is used when talking with friends, family, or in everyday conversations. Using the wrong variety can lead to ridicule. For example, using L in a formal speech or H in casual talking would sound unnatural or weird. This shows how strong the rules are about when using each variety.

2.2.3 Prestige

In many diglossic communities, H is seen as better than L. People think it's more beautiful, more correct, or more real even when they don't speak it fluently. For example, Arabic speakers might say "someone doesn't know Arabic" just because they don't speak Standard Arabic (H), even if they speak Moroccan Arabic (L) very well. Some even deny they use L at all, but when you ask what language they use with their kids or parents, they usually admit it's L (Ferguson, 1959). That shows how much value is placed on H, even if people rely on L every day.

2.2.4 Literary Heritage

Another reason H is so respected is because it's tied to the community's literary past. Most of the classical books, religious texts, and poetry were written in H, and people still look up to these works. Even when modern writers create new texts, they often

try to keep the same old style or use older words to show they're part of that tradition. It's like H connects them to their history.

2.2.5 Acquisition

The acquisition of the High (H) and Low (L) varieties in diglossia differs significantly. People usually learn L at home just by growing up, listening, talking, and picking it up naturally from parents, friends, and neighbors. But H is different. It's taught in schools, religious classes, or by tutors. That's why most people feel more comfortable in L. It's their real first language. H, on the other hand, takes work to master. It's full of grammar rules, and most people never feel totally at ease using it like they do with L.

2.2.6 Stability

Many people think that diglossia is unstable and will eventually disappear, but this is not true. Diglossia can actually survive for centuries. Some communities even use a kind of mix between H and L in semi-formal situations like in the media or speeches where the vocabulary is more classical but the grammar feels easier and more like L. This helps keep the system going by bridging the gap between the two varieties.

2.2.7 Grammar

When you look at grammar, H is usually way more complex than L. For instance, Classical Arabic has noun cases and verb endings, while Moroccan Arabic drops most of those. H uses stricter grammar rules and more categories, which makes it harder to speak casually. That's one reason why people avoid using H in everyday talk.

2.2.8 Lexicon

H and L do share a lot of words, but they also each have their own special vocabulary. H is full of formal and technical terms, words for science, religion, and law. L is packed with casual and local words, especially things from everyday life that you wouldn't hear in a formal setting. Sometimes, H and L have totally different words for

the same thing like how “see” is /ra’ā/ in H and /jāf/ in L. You can usually tell right away which variety someone is using just by their word choice.

2.3 Diglossia and Code-Switching

2.3.1 Definition and Patterns

In communities where people use both a High (H) and a Low (L) variety of the same language, code-switching is just part of everyday life. It’s when people shift from one variety to the other depending on who they’re talking to or what they’re talking about. For example, a teacher might give a history lesson in Standard Arabic (H), but when a student seems confused, the teacher switches to Moroccan Arabic (L) to explain the idea more clearly. That switch isn’t random, it happens for a reason. It could be to make something easier to understand, to sound more formal or respectful, or just to connect better with the listener.

What’s interesting is that this kind of switching follows social rules. In Arabic-speaking countries, it’s totally normal for someone to go from Standard Arabic in a formal speech to Moroccan Arabic when talking with people. It helps create a balance, you still show respect using H, but you connect personally using L.

2.4 Diglossia in Religious Discourse

2.4.1 Language use in religious settings, focusing on Friday sermons

Religious sermons in Morocco demonstrate a dynamic use of language that extends beyond the traditional High/Low division. Bell’s (1984) explain this in his audience design study saying that “Style is essentially speakers’ response to their audience. In audience design, speakers accommodate primarily to their addressee” this means The way we speak changes based on who we are talking to. And we should adjust our speech mainly for the listener. delivering Friday prayer sermon by using a language variety

suitable for the social stratification of the congregations is indeed very important so that the message or content of the sermon can be understood or conveyed. Sugiri, Sodiq, and Yusuf (2019).

While the formal framework of the *xot'ba* remains attached to Standard Arabic due to its religious prestige, the shift to Moroccan Arabic is only used to enhance listening and audience engagement.

2.4.2 Existing research and identified gaps in the literature review

Researches across Arab world have highlighted diglossic use in Friday sermons. Al-Haj Eid's (2019) study of Friday sermons in Jordan shows how preachers switch between Standard Arabic (SA) and Jordanian Colloquial Arabic (JCA) to make their messages clear, engage the audience, and discuss social and political issues. In a similar way, Bassiouney's (2013) study of mosque sermons in Egypt looks at why imams switch between SA and Egyptian Colloquial Arabic (ECA). Imams use the vernacular to feel closer to the audience and to make the sermon more relatable, while using SA to keep a sense of authority. This way, they balance a formal tone with a more casual one to connect better with their listeners. Both studies help us understand how language in religious sermons in the Arab world is used not just to share religious messages, but also to address social, political, and cultural issues. However, even though preachers have access to many sources of knowledge, they rarely include social science ideas in their sermons, suggesting a gap between religious discourse and academic fields.

2.5 Summary

In brief, this literature review has provided an in-depth exploration of diglossia, focusing on the distinction between High (H) and Low (L) language varieties in Arabic speaking communities. It examined their functions, prestige, literary heritage, and methods of acquisition. The review highlighted the stability of diglossia over time, as well as differences in grammar and vocabulary between H and L. It discussed how code-switching naturally occurs between the two varieties, following clear social patterns and contexts. Special attention was given to language use in religious discourse, especially Friday sermons, where preachers switch between Standard and Moroccan Arabic to engage their audience. Studies from Jordan and Egypt show that this switching helps balance authority and reliability. However, a gap remains in integrating social science perspectives into religious sermons. Overall, the review

emphasizes the complex and dynamic nature of diglossia in both everyday and religious communication.

3 Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research design to explore diglossia and code-switching in religious settings. Building on the what I presented in the literature review, this paper seeks to answer the following research question: **how Imams in Moroccan mosques balance Standard Arabic and Moroccan Arabic in Friday sermons.** In order to do that, I will focus in this paper on analyzing natural speech data collected from two Friday sermons to understand how speakers switch between the high (H) and low (L) varieties of Arabic in this formal setting.

3.1 Data Collection

The primary data for this study consist of audio recordings of two Friday sermons delivered in Moroccan mosques. These sermons were purposively selected from areas representing two social classes: middle class and working class. This selection aims to provide authentic examples of diglossic language use in formal religious contexts across different social backgrounds.

Recording live sermons allowed for the collection of spontaneous, naturalistic speech, which is essential for analyzing genuine patterns of code-switching between Standard Arabic (the high variety) and Moroccan Arabic (the low variety). These recordings provide rich linguistic data reflecting real-life language practices in religious discourse.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Explanatory Function

One finding of the analysis is that code-switching occurs to fulfill an explanatory function. The Imams often start by introducing a complex concept in Standard Arabic, and then they switch to Moroccan Arabic to explain what it means, usually with metaphors, examples, or everyday situations.

Example 1: Explanation of “alṣiqa:l” (tie) (Sermon 2)

Standard Arabic (H):

wa l ṣaqlu huwa ṣiqālu l ḥinsāni wa manātʿu t taklīf

“Reason is the ‘tie’ of the human and the basis of accountability.”

Moroccan Arabic (L):

l ṣiqa:l huwa hda:k l ḥabl llika nrəbtʿu bih mənni ka thəkm l bəhi:ma ʔu katrəbtʿha
ba:ʃ ma tmʃi:ʃ

“The ‘tie’ is that rope we use when controlling or tying an animal so it doesn’t wander.”

Comment:

In this example, the Imam uses Moroccan Arabic to explain the metaphor behind the word "tie." This makes the idea of "reason" more relatable by linking it to a real-life image that the listeners already know.

Example 2: Clarification of “alqaḍf” (Slander) (Sermon 2)

Standard Arabic (H):

taḥri:mu z zina: wa l liwa:tʿ wa l qaḍf

“Prohibition of adultery, sodomy, and slander.”

Moroccan Arabic (L):

məni kaṅgu:lu l qaḍf huwa ʔənnak tqu:l ʕla ʃi waḥda hadi:k xa:rʒa tʿfri:q hadi:k
fa:sda w nta maʕəndək dali:l ...

“When we say slander, it means accusing a woman of being immoral or wayward without having any proof ...”

Comment:

Here, the switch to Moroccan Arabic helps explain what the word "slander" really means in a more concrete way. The Imam gives a direct example of how someone might commit this sin especially by accusing someone based only on appearances or assumptions, without any actual proof. This makes the warning feel more real and serious, and it reminds listeners not to judge others without clear evidence.

Example 3 (Sermon 2)

Standard Arabic (H):

wa la: tusrifu: ?innahu la: juhibbu l musrifi:n

“Do not be extravagant; indeed, He does not like the extravagant.”

Moroccan Arabic (L):

ha:da f l ħala:l matʒa:wazf lhadd ?u matfu:tf lqja:s

“This applies to permissible things; do not exceed the limit or go beyond measure.”

Comment:

This part is practical. The Imam makes the Quranic advice feel like something you can follow in daily life. By saying “even with halal things,” he’s warning people not to overdo anything, even good things. It’s simple advice, but it sticks.

Example 4 (Sermon 1):

Standard Arabic (H):

qul: "ʔaʕu:ð billa:h mina ʃʃajta:n ir-raʒzi:m"

“Say: ‘I seek refuge in God from the accursed Satan.’”

Moroccan Arabic (L):

qulha: mən qəlbək w biʔixla:s maʔtaxli:f ʃʃajta:n fi tʕa:ri:qək wa la ɖurjətuħ

“Say it from your heart and sincerely; it wont let Satan or his offspring block your path.”

Comment:

This message feels warm and caring. The Imam is not just quoting the Quran, he is encouraging people to say it with their heart and truly mean it. The Moroccan Arabic here makes the advice feel closer, like it’s coming from someone who wants to protect you.

Discussion:

So, basically, all these examples show how code-switching is used as a tool to explain religious messages in a way people can connect with. It's not just about translating, it's about bringing the meaning to life using examples from everyday Moroccan culture.

When the Imam switches to Moroccan Arabic, the audience understands faster and better because it's their natural language. It also makes the Imam sound more relatable, not just like someone reading a formal text, but more like someone speaking directly to them.

Other studies on religious discourse found the same thing that switching languages helps connect the speaker with the audience and makes abstract or serious ideas feel more personal and easier to act on. (Al-Khatib, 2001; Bassiouney, 2006)

4.2 Moroccan Arabic Tag Inserted for Emphasis

Example 1: Standard Arabic + Moroccan Arabic:

allaḏī faqada ʕaqlahu lā yuḥāsabu fī: ʕarʕi llāh liʔananu maʕandū:f l ʕqal

"Whoever loses his reason is not held accountable in Islamic law [because because he has no sanity]"

Comment:

The Moroccan Arabic tag maʕandū:f l ʕqal is short, but it makes the idea more understandable. It repeats the point in casual speech so that no one misses it. It also helps break up the formal sentence and add a more relaxed tone.

Example 2: Standard Arabic + Moroccan Arabic:

wa tʕ tʕabḏʕi:ru huwa sʕarfu l ma:li fi l ḥara:mi qali:luho w kaθi:ruho sawa:ʔ kilqli:l kilti:r

"Wastefulness is spending money on forbidden things, whether little or much [whether small or large]"

Comment:

The Imam uses Moroccan Arabic to repeat the idea in a rhythmic way: kil qli:l, kil kti:r. It sounds natural and makes the message more memorable. These kinds of phrases catch the listener's attention and give the sermon a conversational touch.

Discussion:

These small insertions in Moroccan Arabic may seem simple, but they actually do a lot. They highlight important points, make the sermon easier to follow, and keep the audience engaged. Instead of getting lost in long formal sentences, listeners get quick reminders and clarifications in their own dialect.

From what I noticed, these tags also show how language can be mixed without losing respect for the religious setting. The Imams still keep the structure of Standard Arabic, but the little touches of Moroccan Arabic help bring the message home.

4.3 Summary

This study shows that the imams use two varieties of Arabic in their sermons: Standard Arabic and Moroccan Arabic. Standard Arabic is used for formal, religious parts such as Quranic verses, important religious terms, and formal advice. It has complex grammar with case endings, formal verb forms, and flexible sentence structure. This variety carries prestige and connects the sermons to the classical Islamic literary tradition.

On the other hand, Moroccan Arabic is used to explain, clarify, and make the religious messages easier to understand for the audience. It uses simpler grammar without case endings and more fixed word order. The imams switch to Moroccan Arabic to give examples, metaphors, or practical advice in everyday language. Sometimes, short Moroccan Arabic phrases are inserted as tags to emphasize important points and keep the listeners engaged.

Overall, the code-switching between Standard and Moroccan Arabic helps balance the need for religious authority and clarity. Standard Arabic adds formality and respect, while Moroccan Arabic makes the message accessible and relatable. This mixing shows how language serves different purposes in religious communication.

5 Conclusion

This study has shown that diglossia, the use of two distinct varieties of Arabic within the same community is a central feature of religious sermons in Morocco. Imams skillfully alternate between Standard Arabic (the High variety) and Moroccan Arabic (the Low variety) during their Friday sermons. Standard Arabic is used for quoting the Quran, delivering formal religious messages, and maintaining the prestige and authority of the sermon. Its complex grammar and historical connection to Islamic tradition make it the appropriate choice for these formal functions.

At the same time, the use of Moroccan Arabic is essential for making religious ideas clear and accessible to the congregation. Imams switch to Moroccan Arabic to explain difficult concepts, give practical advice, and connect with listeners in a more personal and relatable way. This code-switching follows clear social and communicative rules, reflecting the functional separation between the two varieties that is typical of diglossic communities. The practice ensures that the message is both respected and understood by all members of the audience.

Overall, the findings highlight how diglossia remains a stable and effective strategy in Moroccan religious life. The balanced use of Standard and Moroccan Arabic allows imams to uphold religious tradition while also meeting the practical needs of their listeners. This research demonstrates that diglossia is not only about language difference, but also about how speakers adapt their language to serve different purposes in society, preserving heritage, building community, and ensuring effective communication.

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Appendix A

DATA RECORDS

Sermon 1 (IPA transcription):

ælhɑmdu lilla:h rabbi lʃɑ:lami:n, ælhɑmdu lilla:hi ɣɑ:firu ðʃðɑnbi wɑ qɑ:bili
ttʃɑubi ʃɑdi:di lʃiqa:bi ði: ttʃɑul, ælhɑmdu lilla:h almutafaðʃ:ili ʃɑlɑ: mɑn tɑ:bɑ
ʔilɑjhi wɑ ssʃɑlɑ:tu wɑ ssʃɑlɑ:mu ʃɑlɑ: sɑjjidina wɑ nɑbijjina muħɑmmɑd, mɑ:tɑ
wɑ ssʃɑlɑ:tu wɑ ttɑsli:mɑ:tu ʃɑlɑjhi wɑ ʃɑlɑ: ʔɑ:lihi ʔɑjjibi:nɑ ʔɑ::hiri:n
ɑlmɑħddijji:n ɑlmuhtɑdi:n wɑ ʃɑlɑ: mɑn tɑbiʃɑhum wɑ qɑfɑ: biʔɑθɑrihim ʔilɑ:
jɑumi ddi:n, jɑumɑ lɑ: jɑnfɑʃu mɑ:lun wɑ lɑ: bɑnu:n ʔillɑ: mɑn ʔɑtɑ: llɑ:hɑ
biqɑlbini sɑli:m, ʔɑmmɑ: bɑʃd.

fɑjɑ: ʔɑjjuhɑl muslimu:n, jɑ: ʔɑħbɑbɑ rɑsu:li llɑ:hi sɑllɑ llɑhu ʃɑlɑyhi wɑ
ssʃɑlɑ:m wɑjɑ: bɑqɑ:jɑ lɣɑjɾ, ʔiðɑ: ʔɑdrɑknɑ ʔɑnnɑ muħɑ:sɑbɑtɑ nɑfɑsi wɑ
tɑzkiyɑtɑhɑ lissʃulu:ki lħɑsɑni dɑ:ʔimi min qɑwli rrijɑ:ʔi ʃindɑ lmuslimi wɑ
ʔɑnnɑhɑ: ɑssʃɑbi:lu lʔɑmθɑlu ʔilɑ: lħɑjɑ:ti tʃʃɑjjibɑti lɑwʃu:dɑti fi: lqurɑ:ni
lkɑri:m, wɑ ʔɑnnɑ lmutɑkɑllimɑ hunɑ: huwɑ ʔɑllɑ:h wɑ lɑmubɑllighu huwɑ
rɑsu:lo ʔɑllɑ:hi ʃɑllɑ: llɑ:hu ʃɑlɑyhi wɑ ssʃɑllɑ:mɑ wɑ ʃʃɑjʃɑ:nu lɑ: qudrɑtɑ lɑhu
ʃɑlɑ: dduxu:li fi: hɑ:ðɑ lɣɑtt, fɑʔinnɑ ʔɑshɑl tʃʃɑriqi ʔilɑ: ðɑ:likɑ huwɑ
lʔistimsɑ:ku biħɑbli llɑ:hi lɑtʃi:n, min ɣilɑ:li ʔumu:rin ʔɑħɑmmu:hɑ: tibɑ:ʃɑn
mɑ: jɑ:li kɑmɑ: kɑ:nɑ ʔɑ:bɑ:ʔukum wɑ ʔɑzɑdɑ:dukmɑ rɑħimɑhumu ʔɑllɑ:h,
ɑllɑði:nɑ ʔɑ:mɑnu: wɑ tɑʔmɑʔinnu qulu:buhum biðikri llɑ:h, ʔɑlɑ: biðikri
ʔɑllɑ:hi tɑʔmɑʔinnu lqulu:b, ɑllɑði:nɑ ʔɑ:mɑnu: wɑ tɑbɑʃɑt-hum ðuriijɑtu-hum
biʔi:mɑ:nin ɑlħɑqnɑ: bihim ðuriijɑtɑhum, ʔiðɑ: kuntɑ sʃɑ:liħɑn fɑʔinnɑ llɑ:hɑ
tɑʃɑ:lɑ: jɑtɑwɑllɑ: ðɑ:likɑ wɑ julħiqɑ bikɑ ɑð:uriijɑh, wɑ mɑ: ʔɑðinu: min
ʃɑmɑlihim min ʃɑjʔi, kullu mriʔin bimɑ: kɑsɑbɑ rɑħi:n.

fɑʃɑlɑjɑ kɑ jɑ: muslimu mɑ: jɑli: ʔɑwwɑlɑn mɑlɑ:zɑmɑtu ddi:kri fɑʔiðɑ:
ðɑkɑrtɑllɑ:hɑ fɑʔinnɑhɑ jɑðkurok fɑðkuru:ni: ʔɑðkurokmɑ ðkurohu
biʔɑsmɑ:ʔihilħu:snɑ: jɑðkurokmɑ bilʔistizɑ:bɑti lidɑʃɑwɑ:tikum

hijɑ sʃi:iyɑ dijɑl lʔinsɑ:n jixtɑ:r lʔism lli kɑ:jəntʃɑ:bɑq mɑʃ lħɑ:zɑ

lli ʃəndu: w jɑkul jɑ:ɣɑfuro ɣfirhɑ: jɑ:sɑttɑ:ru sturhɑ: lɑ: ʔilɑ:hɑ ʔillɑ: llɑ:h

ttɑoħi:d wəntɑ: ɣɑ:di hətɑ: tɪlqɑ: lkalimɑ:t lli byi:ti tʃttɑ:kɑf

ʃli:hum. mɑlɑ:zɑmɑtu ddi:kri l:bɑ:jin ʃɑn ɑljɑqɑdʃɑ: bilmuro:qɑ:bɑti ddi:ɑʔimɑti

maŝa listəhdʕa:r ʔanna lmasʔala taqtadi: listəhdʕa:r dijəl lŝaql wa bihi
la: jaza:lu lisa:nuka ja: muslim raṭban min ḍikri lla:h walʔaxḍ jura:do mina
lqurʔa:n
wala: jənqaṭiŝ fi: ḥaja:ti lʔinsa:n walisti:ma:ŝi ʔila: wa:ziŝi lqurʔa:n wahuwa
jukallimuk
w juxa:ṭibuk walʔiŝya:ʔu ʔilajhi fi: kulli ma: jaʔmuru bihi wa janha: ŝanhu
qa:la taŝa:la: mutasa:ʔilan ʔafala jatadab:aru:nalqurʔa:na ʔam ŝala: qulu:bin
aqfa:luha inna llaḏ:i:na rtad:u: ŝala: ʔadba:rihim min baŝdi ma: tabajjana lahum
lhuda: ŝfajṭa:nu sawwala lahum waʔamla: lahum qul ʔaŝu:ḏu billa:hi
minaŝfajṭa:ni rrazi:m jebaŝdək minnu: qulha: min qalbk
w biʔixla:s maytaxalliif ŝfajṭa:n fəṭṭari:q dja:lk wala: ḏurri:jtu ʔula:ʔik humu
lxa:sirun ʔaj ʔallaḏi:n la: jafaŝalu:na ma: qulnah ḏa:lika biʔanna lla:ha ma:wla
llaḏi:na ʔa:manu: waʔanna lka:firi:na la: mawla: lahum kama: jazibu ttaʔammul
fi: qawlihi taŝa:la: ṭawi:lan ʔijja:ka naŝbudu: wa ʔijja:ka nastaŝi:n ha:di:
wa:hda lŝuqda: katŝqqad ma: bi:n lxa:liq w lməxlu:q ʔijja:ka naŝbudu wa
ʔijja:ka nastaŝi:n la: naŝbudu ʔilla: ʔanta wa la: nastaŝi:n biʔaḥadin su:wak ma:
tqallab ŝla: lli jḍŝi mŝak wala: lli ja:xuḍ bi:k wala: lli jqu:l lla:h jafŝal li:k di:k
lla:h jafŝal li:k lla:h jarḏi: ŝli:k lla:h jafŝal li:k lla:h jafŝal li:k ŝnu: ha:da:
kertsamma: talab wala: ʔamr ha:da: ra:h ʔamr ṣjdi: assja:dna: katqu:l lla:h
jarḏa: ŝli:k ka: tuqu:l lla:h ŝnu: ydi:r fakkar f ha:di ẓajjidan wa ʔaŝliḥ lisa:nak)
ʔila byiti ṭləb katqu:l "ʔalla:humma ʔinni: ʔasʔaluk" — nasʔaluka lla:humma
ʔamma: baŝ tqu:l "lla:h jifŝal ha:da ʔamr" katŝti:h lilla:h. faʔaḏabu
assulu:ki mŝa: maliki l-mulu:ki la: jaʔti: nasabuhu mŝa: istiḥda:ri ẓala:li rrabbi
lmuxa:tab. kulla ma: qulti:ha: jaḥfadak w jəsatrək w jənsarək. walʔistika:natu
mutlaqan liʔamrihi ḥa:jḏu juqirru lŝabdu mara:tin kḏi:ratan fi: ja:wmin
wa:hidin liŝubu:di:jatihi
lilla:hi taŝa:la: waftiqa:rih ʔila: maŝu:natihi sa:ʔilan ʔijja:hu alhidajata likulli
lʔumu:ri
ma: ḏahara minha: wa ma: batan walŝawni ŝalejha: maŝa ḥusni lxa:timah
hijja li ŝleha: lŝamad. ʔalla:humma ʔaḥsin ŝa:qibatana: fi:l ʔumu:ri kulliha:

waʔazirna: min ɣizji ddu:nja: waʕaḏa:bi lʔa:xirah. ʔaxrizna: mina ddu:nja: fi: su:rah.

lʔinsa:n jətʕləb lla:h ʔan juɣrizahu mina d-dunya: biraʔsin marfu:ʕ w kara:matin marfu:ʕah wa ḏʕikrin ḥasan. θa:nijjan, lmuḥa:fa:ya ʕala:

lʕiba:da:ti wa ʔada:ʔuha: ʔiḏ hi:ja ssila:to bejnək wa bejna lxa:liq.

ʔila: frra:tti: fi:ha: tllaqti: mən lqanba. w ʔila: tllaqti

mən lqanba ma: yatlaqaf fi:n tʕadd, yatzaq ʔu:tʕih liʔannaka na:qis

ɣa:sək tkamməl lmuʕda:l. ma: tləbtʕ mənək ʕafra ʕla: ʕafra [10/10] ... ʔi: xamsa ʕla: ʕafra [5/10]

lmuhimm lijabti:ha: ra:k beɣejr mʕa: r-rabbi lkari:m subḥa:nahu wa taʕa:la:, ʔafur, ʕaku:r, wadu:d, ḥali:m, ʔayfiru ḏḏunu:ba lilʕiba:d.

fafi:ha: min ʔasra:ri t-tazkija linnufu:si wa taḥlijatiha: faḏa:ʔil ma: naḏʕarta mina lʔa:ja:ti lqurʔa:nija

wa dallat ʕalejha: alʔaḥadi:θu n-nabawijja ʔila: kunna: kanqraw lʔaḥadi:θ ʔukanztamʕu:

faddar, ʔu nʕamʕu l-wlida:t wal bni:ja:t wan zaḃddu lkutaji:b ʔu nqraw fasʕəl min fusʕu:l ddin

ʔaw lqurʔa:n, ʔaw ʔejru, ʔaw ʔejru, badal lma:kla wa ʕfara:b, wa ḏʕḏʕaḥk wa laʕb, ʔu: hna:.

ʔila: maʕja:ʕ lʔinsa:n men ha:d ʕfi:...

ʔaktiru: mina sʕsʕala:ti wa sʕsʕala:m ʕala: sajjidi lɣalqi wa ḥabi:b ilḥaqq (duʕa:ʔ ilɣa:tima

Sermon 2 (IPA transcription):

wa l ʕaqlu huwa ʕiqālu l ʔinsāni wa manātʕu t taklīf l ʕiqa:l huwa hda:k l ḥabl llika nrəbtʕu bih mənni ka thəkm l bəhi:ma ʔu katrəbtʕha ba:ʕ ma tmʕi:ʕ wa sumiya l ʕaqlu ʕaqlan liʔannahu yamnaʕu l ʔinsāna mina linzilāqi wa manātʕu ttaklīfi bimaʕnā ʔila makənti:ʕ bʕaqlək ʕfarʕ rfaʕ ʕlik ttakli:f allaḏī faqada ʕaqlahu lā yuḥāsabu fi: ʕarʕi llāḥ liʔananu maʕəndu:ʕ l ʕqal al ʔinsānu llaḏī yuḥāsabu yajibu ʔan yakūna musliman bāliyan ʕāqilan ʔilā: ʔāxiri ʔinnamā yurīdu ʕ ʕaytānu ʔan yūqiʕa baynakumu l ʕadawata wa l bayḏʕāʔa fi l xamri wa

I maysiri wa yas'uddakum ʕan ʔikri llāhi wa ʕani ss'alāt fahal ʔantum
 muntahun jaʕni hal lenthaytu:m waf ma byi:tu:f tbaʕdu: w thajdu: mən ha:dʒi
 faqad ʔahāt'a ddīnu laʕrād'a alʕird'u huwa ʕarafu wa nmasl wa huwa mā
 yataʕallaqu bi ʕarafu lʔinsān ʔ wlida:tu ʔ l kara:ma dja:lu wa ʔahāt'a ddīn al
 aʕrād'a bi tafriʕātīn taḥfad'uhā wa tazʕaluhā fī nufu:si nnāsi mus'ānatan
 muhtarama taḥri:mu z zina: wa l liwa:t' wa l qaḏ'f mənni kaḅgu:lu l qaḏ'f huwa
 ʔənnak tqu:l ʕla ʕi waḥda hadi:k xa:rza t't'ri:q hadi:k fa:sda w nta maʕəndək
 dali:l wla ʕhu:d wla jdik wla jxallik maʕəndəkʕ l ḥaqq tkəlləm f ʕi waḥəd u tqu:l
 hadi:k raḥa xa:rza t't'ri:q wla hada:k raḥ fa:səd wla hada:k raḥ kifəsad wla
 hada:k raḥ kada ʕi:r rfaqt lik wla ban lik waḥəd l mənḏ'ar muʕajjan ʔaw qālti
 ʕlih huk Jazib kaḏa:lika tazannubu l mulika:t fī l ma:li bi ʕtiba:rihi wasi:latan
 taqu:mu ʕalajha: l ḥaja:tu wa tataḥaqqaqu biha: l mas'a:liḥu ad'dunjawi:jatu wal
 uxrawi:ja hadi: x's's'ʕu jaʕtaqad'ha kul muslim w kul mu:man al ma:lu ma:lu
 l'fa:hi wa l ʔinsa:nu mustaxlafun fi:h wa la: tusrifu: ʔinnahu la: juḥibbu l
 musrifi:n ha:da f l ḥala:l matza:wif l ḥadd ʔo ma tfu:tf l qja:s wa t' t'abḏ'i:r al
 farqu bajna l ʔisra:fi wa t' t'abḏ'i:r al ʔisra:f fl ḥala:l tzi:bu mən l ḥala:l w ta:klu
 mən l ḥala:l wa lakiin tfu:t l qja:s ktr mən l la:zəm nta hna ʕir kaḏ'jaʕ t'
 t'abḏ'i:r wa law darham ḥa:za zəbti:ha mən l ḥarəm ʔu ḥa:za nfaqtī:ha f l
 ḥara:m ra:h t'abḏ'i:r wa t' t'abḏ'i:ru huwa s'arfu l ma:li fi l ḥara:mi qali:luho w
 kaḥi:ruho sawa:ʔ kilqli:l kilti:r qa:la taʕa:la: wa la: tubaḏ'ḏ'ir t'abḏ'i:ra ʔinna l
 mubad'ḏ'iri:na ka:nu: ʔixwa:na ʕfaja:t'i:n qa:la rasu:lu l'la:hi s'alla: l'la:hu
 ʕalajhi wa sallam la: taz'u:lu qad'ama: ʕabdin jawma l qija:mati ḥatta: jusʔala
 ʕan ʔarbaʕ : ʕan ʕumrihi fi:ma ʔafna:h, wa ʕan ʕasadihi fi:ma ʔabla:h, wa ʕan
 ʕilmihī ma: ʕamila bih, wa ʕan ma:lihi min ʔajna ktasaba-hu wa fi:ma ʔanfaqa-
 h. ha:ḏa ʕallū wa sallimū ʕala: ḥabi:bi.

1,049 words